

EUROPEAN MIDDLEWARE INITIATIVE

PSEUDONYMITY CLIENT INSTALLATION GUIDE

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Pseudonymity Client: Configuration

Introduction

EMI Pseudonymity System is meant for providing its users a way to hide their true identity behind a pseudonymous identity. The term refers to a lesser degree of anonymity, as the relationships between the pseudonyms and the true identities can be revealed eg. in the cases of misuse. Users obtain pseudonymous identities from the Pseudonymity Service by using their existing Grid identity for authentication and authorization. The service registers the newly issued pseudonyms to the VO's attribute authority as aliases to the users' existing certificates. The service is accessed with a dedicated client tool.

This guide explains how to install the client-side.

Installation

Make sure that the host has NTP properly configured. Clock skew between the client and the server may cause many types of failures.

The pseudonymity client can be installed from the EMI repositories. The package name `pseudonymity-ui`.

For SL5/SL6, the installation can be done using the command `yum install pseudonymity-ui`.

Configuration File

The pseudonymity client is a command-line tool without a configuration file: all the configuration options are given as arguments to the tool.

Usage

For the instructions, see Pseudonymity Client User Guide

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